

CHARACTERISTICS OF MANAGING THE ACTIVITY OF BUILDING MATERIALS MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

This article characteristics of the management of construction materials production enterprises light up given.

Keywords: Modern enterprise, non-profit, construction material, monopolization, public debt, efficiency.

A modern enterprise is an independent economic entity based on various forms of ownership that produces goods, in particular, public goods, provides services, carries out scientific research and commercial (non-commercial) activities in order to achieve economic and social efficiency. However, building materials production enterprises The lack of a clear strategy and ultimate goal for the optimization of its borders, the clear definition of the scope of enterprises and its scope has led to a situation with a number of deformations in the national economy, including:

- maintaining a high level of monopolization, the existence of oligarchic corruption structures, a high level of relative poverty (the difference between the incomes of the poorest and richest population groups),

- high level of state debt, low solvency against the background of insufficiently effective use of enterprise potential. In general, in developed countries, the efficiency of private property management is determined according to the chosen task. The maximum reduction of the array of property objects is the main condition for improving its management. The success criteria for this are:

- an increase in the value of state property and an increase in the amount of paid wages;

- the total growth of capitalization reflecting the total calculated value of commercial assets;

- the amount of taxes paid (an increase in tax payments is a positive result);

The existence of effective demand is the best stimulator of the market economy. Public demand can be activated not only through direct purchases, but also by increasing wages and investments in controlled enterprises. This indicator evaluates the prospects for the development of construction materials production enterprises of the economy. In general, the characteristics of the role and activity of enterprises in the conditions of a developed market are based on the following:

- absolute development of activities and economic sectors (defense industry, railway transport, etc.) that play a leading role in ensuring the appropriate level of national security of the country;

- filling the market gaps and areas of meeting the social needs of the society, where subjects of other forms of ownership do not want to carry out business activities due to low income (even complete unprofitability). Development cannot be ensured without adequate satisfaction of these social needs;

- development of measures to ensure national interests in strategic production areas, to protect against expansion of guaranteed foreign capital;

- they eliminate the crisis conditions of this development due to the state's influence on the negative factors of economic development and stricter regulation and coordination of economic activity;

- they are an effective means of regulating prices in the domestic market, soft intervention of the state to establish price balance in order to protect the layers of the population in need of social protection;

- ensuring the presence of the state in capital-intensive types of economic activity that cannot provide the creation and application of modern technologies due to the lack of private capital. It should be noted that in this regard, the activities of the private sector have caused a number of problems, including:

- implementation of secret privatization schemes of state property under the guise of state (national) joint stock and holding companies;

- transfer of some of the state-owned enterprises and state stock packages to private enterprises;

- insufficient internal control in enterprises and unqualified, inexperienced ordinary members of enterprise management;

- absence of a typical corporate structure and activity goals and violation of financial and tax discipline;

- limited information about the company's activities for the company and shareholders, as well as lack of audit of the company by external auditors.

In this regard, Y.V.Svetlichnaya in its scientific researches emphasizes that in many cases ineffective activity is connected with unsuccessful reforms and

management of entities by new owners. Based on these opinions, in our opinion, the main problems that need to be solved in order to maintain, manage and improve enterprises should be the following. In particular:

- lack of a modern strategy for the development of the private sector;
- dispersion and inconsistency of the functions of management bodies of the enterprise;
- use of inefficient management in the interests of interested business groups for subsequent appropriation or sale of enterprises;
- lack of own funds for innovative and investment development of enterprises, high percentage of loans. In our opinion, the following measures should be taken at the state level to solve these problems. Including:
 - conducting financial-economic and independent economic diagnostics in construction material production enterprises;
 - clearly defining functions, powers and responsibilities for results and consequences;
 - development of plans reflecting short-term concepts, programs and solutions to problems;
 - Development and adoption of a general strategy for the development of building materials production enterprises until 2030;
 - development of a collection mechanism and improvement of management in order to increase its funds in construction material production enterprises;
 - implementation of state protection of construction material production enterprises at the stage of bankruptcy and development of preferential conditions for taxation of bankrupt enterprises;
 - to protect the rights of construction materials production enterprises, to take measures to prevent the activity of objects in the hidden economy;
 - organizing an "open day" for non-state and foreign investments and expanding opportunities (including leasing, leasing, concession terms).

Another way to increase the efficiency of construction materials production enterprises is to increase the efficiency of the decision-making process. This can be achieved with the help of modern information technologies. Relevant, accurate and timely information is a prerequisite for making high-quality management decisions. Ensuring sustainable labor productivity requires the participation of leaders at all levels in this process (Table 1).

Table 1

A list of tasks necessary to achieve the maximum value of construction materials production enterprises

Formulation of the enterprise development strategy and precise determination of the stages of its implementation	The use of innovative technologies that ensure the growth of production and labor efficiency, guarantee the high quality of products and environmental control
Optimizing the structure of enterprise financing sources	To improve the corporate culture and convey to each employee the need to increase the value of the enterprise
Ensuring the liquidity of the company's assets and striving to reduce the period of circulation of working capital	To contribute to the improvement of the business reputation and image of the enterprise

Building materials production enterprises

The implementation of the efficiency management process in construction materials production enterprises should be carried out by creating an appropriate system, the basis of which is the indexes, coefficients and performance indicators developed for individual units and for the entire enterprise. The development of such systems should be carried out by employees responsible for the state of labor efficiency in the enterprise. It is necessary to advocate a value-based approach to performance management and define it as a process aimed at achieving the maximum value of the enterprise, which involves solving a set of necessary tasks.

The organizational support system for managing the efficiency of construction materials production enterprises is a set of internal structural services and divisions of the enterprise that ensures the development and adoption of management decisions on certain issues of profit planning, formation, distribution and use. interconnected set. The general principles of forming the organizational structure of enterprise management provide for two types of management centers - hierarchical and organic organization. According to E. Neely, it is appropriate to implement the following in the process of efficiency management:

- determination of the mission of the enterprise;
- assessment of management activity in retrospect;
- taking into account the multifaceted aspects of management and forming the expected result of the activity. In our opinion, it is appropriate to express the cycle of efficiency management of construction materials production enterprises in 5 stages,

starting with effective planning and ending with rewarding employees for their effective work (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The main stages of the performance management cycle

E. Holdsworth and D. Jirasin, performance management includes joint work, long-term thinking, human capital formation and customer loyalty. It evaluates leaders in human capital formation, employee motivation, employee development and management. Scientists identify two methods of performance management:

- 1) development of efficiency, prospective motivation and professional training of employees at the workplace;
- 2) performance measurement that holds employees accountable and evaluates their contribution to the overall product of the enterprise.

Performance management is integrated with all aspects of enterprise management and decision-making processes, connecting all areas of enterprise activity in order to achieve the best results.

To sum up, the main task of production efficiency management in the market economy is to ensure the ability of the enterprise to survive, adapt to market changes and use new opportunities. These tasks are faced not only by performance management managers, but also by all other managers of the enterprise. At the same time, productivity is the source of all economic results, and productivity is a sign of production efficiency. It is important that production efficiency does not affect productivity, on the contrary, the result is more visible in the external environment, in the consumer during the exploitation of the product, while productivity characterizes the internal production process.

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